

ESA Climate Change Initiative CCI+

Annex to Climate Research Data Package

SNOW
cci

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Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim

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<p>Abstract:</p> <p>The European Space Agency (ESA) Climate Change Initiative aims to generate high quality Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) derived from long-term satellite data records to meet the needs of climate research and monitoring activities. The main goal of the <i>snow_cci</i> project is to generate homogeneous, well-calibrated, long-term time series of the key snow cover variables snow area extent and snow mass for climate applications. <i>snow_cci</i> Option 2 <i>Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim</i> has advanced the original CryoClim binary product to an FSC product.</p> <p>This document describes the outcome of the product generation from the <i>snow_cci</i> Option 2 project. The Climate Research Data Package – time series of products – are produced for fractional snow cover (FSC) based on multi-sensor/multi-temporal analysis of data from the sensors AVHRR, SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS. An estimate of the uncertainty at the per-pixel level is available as a separate data layer in the product.</p>			
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA Contract. Responsibility for the contents resides in the author or organisation that prepared it.</p>			
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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose and Scope

The European Space Agency (ESA) Climate Change Initiative aims to generate high-quality Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) derived from long-term satellite data records to meet the needs of climate research and monitoring activities, including the detection of variability and trends, climate modelling, and aspects of hydrology and meteorology. The Climate Research Data Package (CRDP) for the ESA CCI+ snow Option-2 project *Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim* closely follows the CRDP of the *snow_cci* baseline project. The product, *snow_cci* CryoClim fractional snow cover (FSC), is based on multi-sensor/multi-temporal analysis of data from the sensors AVHRR, SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS. The retrieved entity represents snow on the ground (SCFG). An estimate of the uncertainty at the per-pixel level is available as a separate data layer in the product (RMSE SCFG).

1.2. Document Structure

Following this introduction section, the product time series generated within the Option 2 - *Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim*, is presented in Section 2.

1.3. Applicable and Reference Documents

[AD-1] Phase 1 of the ESA Climate Change Initiative CCI+ New ECVS (Snow). ESRIN Contract No: 4000124098/18/I-NB.

[AD-2] Climate Change Initiative Extension (CCI+) Phase 1 – New Essential Climate Variables (Annex E: Snow ECV (Snow_cci), ESA-CCI-PRGM-EOPS-SW-17-0032.

[AD-3] Technical Proposal (Part 3) in response to ESA Climate Change Initiative Phase 1 ESA ITT AO/1-9041/17/I-NB, ENVEO Innsbruck, Austria.

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[RD-2] Notarnicola, C., Marin, C., Schwaizer, G., Nagler, T., Luojus, K., Derksen, C., Mortimer, C., Wunderle, S., Nägeli, K. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV: Product Validation Plan, version 2.0, October 2021.

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- [RD-8] Solberg, R., Killie, M. A., Rudjord, Ø., Eastwood, S., Sørensen, A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Data Access Requirements Document, version 1.1
- [RD-9] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Salberg, A.-B., Killie, M. A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Algorithm Development Plan, version 1.0
- [RD-10] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Salberg, A.-B., Killie, M. A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Product Validation Plan, version 1.0
- [RD-11] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Killie, M. A., Sørensen, A. M., Eastwood, S. (2021) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document, version 2.0.
- [RD-12] Salberg, A.-B., Solberg, R. (2021) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to End-to-End ECV Uncertainty Budget, version 2.0.
- [RD-13] Solberg, R. and Rudjord, Ø. (2022) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to System Specification Document, version 1.0.
- [RD-14] Marin, C., Premier, V., Rudjord, Ø. and Solberg, R. (2022) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Product Validation and Intercomparison Report, version 1.0.
- [RD-15] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Killie, M. A., Sørensen, A. M., Eastwood, S. (2022) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Product User Guide, version 1.0.

1.4. Acronyms

AVHRR	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CP	Contractual Phase

DARD	Data Access Requirement Document
DMSP	Defence Meteorological Satellite Program
ESA	European Space Agency
FSC	Fractional Snow Cover
GAC	Global Area Coverage
MetOp	European Meteorological Operational Satellite
MODIS	Moderate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NDSI	Normalized Difference Snow Index
NH	Northern Hemisphere
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
PMR	Passive Microwave Radiometer
PVP	Product Validation Plan
SCF	Snow Cover Fraction
SCFG	Snow Cover Fraction, snow on the Ground
SCFV	Snow Cover Fraction, Viewable snow
SMMR	Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer
SSM/I	Special Sensor Microwave/Imager
SSMIS	Special Sensor Microwave Imager / Sounder
SWE	Snow Water Equivalent
WGS	World Geodetic System

2. PRODUCT

The overall aim of the *snow_cci* CryoClim fractional snow cover (FSC) climate data record is to provide one of the longest snow cover extent time series available with global coverage and without hindrance from clouds and polar night. This has been achieved by utilising the best features of optical and passive microwave radiometer (PMR) observations of snow using a sensor-fusion algorithm generating a consistent time series of global FSC products (Solberg et al. 2014, 2015; Rudjord et al. 2015).

AVHRR sensors aboard the satellites NOAA-7, -9, -11, -14, -16, -18, -19, MetOp-A and MetOp-B have been used as the optical data source, and SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS sensors aboard the satellites Nimbus 7, DMSP F8, DMSP F11, and from DMSP F13 to DMSP F18, respectively, have been used as PMR data source. To achieve temporally stable data, we use fundamental climate data records (FCDRs) as input provided by EUMETSAT Climate Monitoring Satellite Application Facility (CM SAF). These data cover the period 01.01.1982-31.12.2020 for optical (Karlsson et al. 2020) and 01.01.1982-31.12.2015 for PMR (Fenning et al. 2017). To make an interim extension of the time series until 31.12.2023, we have used interim data (near real-time data) with AVHRR GAC data for optical used by EUMETSAT to generate CLARA A3 products (Karlsson et al. 2023) and for PMR operational SSMIS data from NOAA (NOAA 2023). The CryoClim multi-sensor/multi-temporal concept for fusion of optical and PMR data for retrieval of FSC is based on a hidden Markov model (HMM) where 10%-level FSC states are modelled. The last part of the algorithm carries out a weighted interpolation between 10%-FSC states to reach 1%-FSC precision [RD-11].

The FSC product represents snow on the ground (SCFG) and is processed in a 5 km grid resolution and finally projected to a latitude/longitude grid of 0.05° resolution (Table 2.1). The CRDP characteristics are provided in Table 2.2. A product example is provided in Figure 2.1 (FSC) and Figure 2.2 (associated uncertainty). There are no data gaps in the product time series. However, there are periods of reduced product quality due to sensor problems in the 1980s and 1990s (Table 2.3).

Table 2.1: CryoClim FSC time series characteristics.

<i>Subject</i>	<i>Description</i>
Thematic variable	Fractional Snow Cover (FSC)
Retrieval algorithm	CryoClim multi-sensor/multi-temporal fusion of optical and PMR (Solberg et al. 2015; Rudjord et al. 2015) advanced in <i>snow_cci</i> Option 2 to obtain FSC [RD-7]
Uncertainty algorithm	Salberg et al. 2021 [RD-12]
Satellite(s)	NOAA-7, -9, -11, -14, -16, -18, -19, MetOp-A, MetOp-B; Nimbus-7, DMSP F8, - F11, - F13 -- F18
Sensor(s)	AVHRR, SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS
Geographical domain(s)	Global
Temporal resolution	Daily

Start date time series	1 January 1982
End date time series	31 December 2023
Grid size	0.05°
Projection/datum	Geographical (lat/lon)/WGS 84
File format	NetCDF4, CF-v1.9
Product version	Prototype version

Table 2.2: CryoClim FSC CRDP characteristics.

Subject	CryoClim multi-sensor/multi-temporal FSC CRDP
Data volume	35 GB
DOI	doi:10.5285/f4654030223445b0bac63a23aaa60620
Data catalogue access	https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/f4654030223445b0bac63a23aaa60620/

Figure 2.1: CryoClim FSC product example for 1 April 2014.

Figure 2.2: CryoClim FSC product uncertainty estimate example for 1 April 2014.

The periods of reduced product quality are briefly explained in the following (Table 2.3). Bias associated with Nimbus 7 SMMR and DMSP F-8 SSM/I has been observed, in particular in summer period with almost only wet and patchy snow present. SMMR did not have the 85 GHz channel and had a somewhat different set of channel frequencies. The 85 GHz channel on the first SSM/I instrument failed early in the mission. The lack of 85 GHz channels on both satellites and the channel differences between the instruments have resulted in somewhat variable retrieval algorithm performance. A tailored algorithm is used with data from Nimbus 7 and DMSP F-8. However, the performance deviate from that of the algorithm we use with other SSM/I and SSMIS instruments. A positive bias appears in the retrieval results, and it is largest for DMSP F8. The problem seems to be associated with patchy (and probably wet) snow cover. The bias seems to be most pronounced in the summer season. We recommend caution for regions of patchy/wet snow in the summer period for the years 1982-1991.

There are periods of unfavourable illumination conditions with the early NOAA satellites. The NOAA satellites do not include any system to stabilise their orbit, resulting in orbital drift and therefore acquisitions progressively earlier (for morning satellites) and later (for afternoon satellites). At very low solar angles, the discrimination power of the optical retrieval algorithm is reduced, resulting in more mixture between snow and clouds. The problem is most prominent when data from only one satellite is available (in particular NOAA-12). When more satellites became available and satellites were launched into an orbit with equatorial passage time closer to noon in the late 1990s, the problem became less pronounced. In the last 20 years there has been more redundancy (more sensors in orbit) and therefore no periods of reduced quality.

Table 2.3: Periods of reduced product quality in the CryoClim FSC time series.

Start date	End date	Reason
01.01.1982	09.07.1987	Reduced discrimination power due to fewer channels on Nimbus 7 SMMR
01.04.1989	18.12.1991	Loss of 85.5 GHz channel DMSP F8 SSM/I
18.12.1991	01.01.1992	Larger acquisition errors due to elliptical orbit
14.09.1994	19.01.1995	Unfavourable illumination conditions due to dependency on NOAA 12 only

For the whole time series, there are 27 days with neither optical nor PMR retrieval (Table 2.4). These are individual days and not series of days in a row. The multi-sensor/time-series algorithm [RD-11] handles this by making a best estimate of snow cover, based on days both prior to and following after the lack of data. This will not reduce the quality of the snow maps much for days without data as long as they are just individual days.

Table 2.4: List of days with no input data (neither optical nor PMR for either hemisphere).

Dates with no satellite data			
19820529	19830806	19841206	19850216
19820531	19830921	19850204	19850218
19820926	19830923	19850206	19850220
19830727	19830925	19850208	19850222
19830729	19840115	19850210	19850224
19830731	19840410	19850212	19860315
19830802	19840723	19850214	

The algorithm estimating the uncertainty associated with the FSC maps [RD-12] needs observations of covariates from the same day as data applied for the FSC product. These covariates are partly based on data from PMR sensors. Hence, estimates of uncertainty could not be produced for days lacking PMR acquisitions (Table 2.5).

Table 2.5: Overview over days per year with no uncertainty estimate for either hemisphere.

Year	Number of days without uncertainty estimate
1982	5
1983	14
1984	5
1985	22
1986	1
1988	6
2008	2
2021	1
2022	1

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